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An Evaluation of the Compatibility of the 2019 Turkish Curriculum (The Case of Iğdır Province)

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to examine the curriculum alignment of the current program in line with the opinions of Turkish teachers based on the flexibility of the 2019 Turkish Language Curriculum. The study group for the research consists of a total of 153 teachers, including 40 Turkish teachers who participated in the semi-structured interview in Iğdır in the 2020–2021 academic year and 113 Turkish teachers who gave their opinions about the achievements in order to measure the accessibility levels of the achievements. When the participant comments are examined, it is seen that their statements emphasize the content of the program in terms of intensity and time. It should be noted that teachers express more curriculum fidelity than curriculum alignment. However, it can be said that the concept of curriculum alignment is considered here as a central program implementation algorithm. It can be said that teachers mostly emphasize inner harmony with the alignment of goals. In addition, stating that the achievements are realized within the framework of texts and activities shows that teachers only adhere to the texts and activities in the text book. It was concluded that the students had difficulties in the application because of problems related to the program, and this might be related to local factors.

Keywords: Low Case, Comma, Paper Template, Abstract, Keywords, Introduction

1. Introduction

The fact that an educated population constitutes a whole society has made teaching and curriculum important not only for today but also for the future education services of the country. When the subject matter is Turkish, that is, "language," it becomes even more important (Aksan, 2015). Language is a structure that is related to, and even creates, other fields and disciplines such as science, art, and technique, all of which are inextricably linked to humans and society. This structure also forms a part of material and spiritual culture. Therefore, people use their ancestors, history, literature, and briefly, culture, while speaking their mother tongue. In this case, it depends on the training given to the students in the curricula and the implementation of the curriculum by the teachers as the implementers of the curriculum. For many reasons, language instruction is crucial to optimizing a student's success. Firstly, it enables individuals to adapt themselves to their countries. Secondly, language enables individuals to open themselves up to different sources in different areas (Eminolu & Tanrkulu, 2018). In elementary school, students learn to read and write at an early age. By the end of the second term of the third

grade, students are able to read and write fluently without interruption. In this day and age, being able to read, write, and do basic math are all critical life skills. Changes in communication, information sharing, and technology in general are occurring at a breakneck pace around the globe in the twenty-first century. Because of the rapidity with which information is being created and consumed, humanity's future rests on our ability to both use and create information. In such a setting, quality education and the instruction of reading and writing, which is its foundation, are necessary (Can & Yavuz, 2017; Güneş, 2003).

This research aims to assist Turkish teachers and curriculum development experts by providing data on how the Turkish curriculum is delivered to students in the province of Idr, which has distinct language and dialect characteristics. In this study, the compatibility of the 2019 Turkish Language Curriculum was evaluated in line with the opinions of Turkish teachers. Thus, the problems encountered regarding the current situation were determined, and the solution proposals developed for these problems contributed to the field. As a result, it is to reveal the compatibility of the current program in line with the opinions of Turkish teachers, based on the flexibility of the 2019 Turkish Course Curriculum. In this way, the problems encountered during the implementation of the curriculum were identified, and solutions were proposed for them.

2. Method

This research was designed according to the case study model, one of the qualitative research designs. Qualitative research can be accepted as a credible research method when it allows for the discovery and understanding of complex issues and when holistic, in-depth research is required (Patton, 2002:14). "The most basic feature of the qualitative case study is the in-depth investigation of one or more cases." In other words, factors related to a situation (environment, individuals, events, processes, etc.) are investigated with a holistic approach. It focuses on how they affect and are affected by the relevant situation. Case studies frequently use more than one data collection method in order to obtain a rich variety of data that can be confirmed (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006: 77; Aytaçlı, 2012).

2.1 Participant (Subject) Characteristics

The study group of the research consists of a total of 153 teachers, including 40 Turkish teachers who participated in the semi-structured interview in Iğdır in the 2020-2021 academic year, and 113 Turkish teachers who gave their opinions in order to reveal the actualization levels of the achievements in the curriculum. The sample of the study was formed by easy sampling method.

2.2 Data Collection

A semi-structured interview form was used as a data collection tool in the study. These forms were prepared in two parts in accordance with the purpose of the research. In the first part, there are questions about the personal information of Turkish teachers. In statements regarding personal characteristics, the appropriate option is marked with an (X) sign. In the second part, there are 8 questions that consider the practices of Turkish teachers in the classroom and ask for their statements about program compatibility.

Before preparing the interview questions, a literature review was made and draft questions were prepared for the data collection tool from studies on similar subjects. The draft questions were developed by taking the opinions of two experts and necessary corrections were made.

As the second data collection tool in the study, the scale, which asked teachers to give a value between 10 and 100 for each acquisition, was prepared on the Google form. While the form was being prepared, the most recurring achievements of the 5,6,7 and 8th grade reading, writing, listening/watching and speaking skills in the 2019 Turkish curriculum.

Validity and Reliability of The Research

Internal validity and external validity to ensure the validity and reliability of the research; Studies on internal reliability and external reliability have been carried out.

Internal Validity: Credibility

The internal validity or credibility of a study is related to whether the interpretations reflect reality (Yldrm & imşek, 2005). To ensure consistency in the data collection, analysis, and interpretation processes, the interview questions were first prepared as a draft by conducting a literature review. The prepared questions were developed step by step by taking the opinions of two experts, and necessary corrections were made. To ensure consistency, an opinion chart based on 10-100 scoring of achievements taken directly from the program was created. Turkish teachers were asked interview questions in the same order and tone of voice. The researcher did not interfere with the views and answers of Turkish teachers, and he also avoided expressing his own feelings and thoughts. In order to increase credibility in the research, both data variation and method variation were employed. For this reason, both the word clouds were analyzed with different methods, and the opinions of the participants were included. Accordingly, it was checked whether the findings obtained constitute a meaningful whole, based on irrelevant concepts and the statements of the participants. In addition, a conceptual framework was created based on the relevant literature (Tuncel, 2008).

External Validity: Transferability

Transferability refers to the generalizability of findings and results to similar situations, plans, or events. For this reason, it has been tried to provide transferability by describing the research process, research model, data sources, data collection tools, data collection process, data analysis and interpretation, and how the findings are organized in detail and based on the literature (Tuncel, 2008; Yldrm & imşek, 2005).

Internal Confidence: Consistency

The consistency of a qualitative researcher is expressed through triangulation, expert review, position, and supervision (Merriam, 2013: 213). It has been tried to ensure the consistency of the research by resorting to "data diversity," referring to "expert opinion," and explaining the "researcher's position." In addition, in order to ensure consistency, the opinions of the participants were presented by making direct quotations without adding any comments and without any reference to the researchers' comments (Tuncel, 2008; Coşkun, 2016). In order to ensure consistency, word clouds were also examined together with the views of the participants, so that they were not tied to only one analysis unit.

External Reliability: Confirmability

The repeatability of qualitative research in similar groups is related to its confirmability (Yldrm & imşek, 2005). In order to ensure the confirmability of the research, the researcher stated his position, defined the individuals who were the data source in the research in detail, defined the method and stages of the research, including data collection, analysis, and interpretation, reached results in a clear and detailed manner, and gave information about the research environment (Coşkun, 2016).

2.4 Ethics

Research ethics are as important as the validity and reliability of a study. Ethics, in its most basic form, is a necessary condition for obtaining valid and reliable information. Unethical information may contain distorted and biased information. As a result (Coşkun, 2016:100-101):

- Necessary permissions have been obtained from the relevant institutions and individuals to carry out applications in the study area.
- Participants were interviewed and informed about the purpose of the research; interviews were held on a voluntary basis.
- A suitable ground has been prepared for teachers to express themselves comfortably.
- The purpose of the research and how the data will be collected are explained in detail.
- The researcher avoided directing questions and shared his personal impressions during the interviews and observations.
- Findings are presented truthfully and openly. Every positive or negative result has been reported.
- Information that would decipher the participants was avoided, and the

participants were expressed by coding. While the researchers were coding, each of them was coding according to a number and their professional experience and graduation type, for example, Turkish teacher 10 (1–9 years, undergraduate).

2.5 Data Analysis

The content analysis method was used in the analysis of the data. The basic process in content analysis will be to collect similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes and to interpret it in a way that the reader can understand (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006:227). The coding was shaped according to the concepts obtained from the qualitative data. While analyzing qualitative data, a text analysis tool was used in the MATLAB program (matlabtextanalyticstoolbox). TextAnalyticsToolbox™ provides algorithms and visualizations for preprocessing, analyzing, and modeling text data. While analyzing the data, calculations were made considering the analysis units. The encodings were exhibited in two situations: words and sentences. The analyses are handled by MATLAB according to the frequency of the words, and the most frequently repeated words are expressed in larger fonts, centrally, and in red forms. When the unit of analysis was considered "the most frequently used word," word clouds were used. These word clouds show word frequency analysis applied to raw text data and a processed version. While preparing the word cloud, conjunctions such as less than a certain letter and or were removed. As a result, it was attempted to focus on meaningful words, and the data was cleaned as a result. Secondly, the comments were examined by the n-gram counting method. An "n-gram" is a bunch of n consecutive words. For example, a bigram (where n = 2) is a double-consecutive word like "heavy precipitation." A unigram (where n = 1) is a single word. A bag-n-gram model records how many times different n-grams appear in documents. More information about word order can be found in the original text data using the one-n-gram model. For example, a bag-n-gram model is better suited for capturing short phrases that appear in text, such as "heavy precipitation" and "stormy winds" (TextAnalyticsToolbox, 2020: 7). Here it is possible to sort words according to their repetition in double, triple, quadruple, and more. There is no standard method for choosing this order. In general, analysis was made according to which n-gram was the most significant. In other words, if the most meaningful structure is a 3-word grouping, the data were analyzed as triples. Since the analysis was done in Turkish sentences, we just put three samples of the results in the figures when considering non-native Turkish speakers. Thirdly, it was examined in terms of different combinations according to the theme model. A topic model explores key topics in a text and extracts word possibilities on those topics (TextAnalyticsToolbox, 2020: 16). In this way, it allows for possible interpretations within the text. Fourthly, the statements of the participants were taken as a basis. At this point, the comments of the participants were based on the above word cloud, n-gram counting, and theme model data. Fifth, the opinions of the participants about the achievements and percentage are given. In order to analyze the data in the table more clearly, the percentage contributions of all items were added together, divided by the product of 100 by the number of items, and multiplied by 100 (total percentage/(number of items*100))*100. Thus, the frequency ratio of each dimension was expressed as a percentage (Duran and Topal, 2021).

2.6. The Role of the Researcher

The role of the researcher in qualitative research is to try to reach the feelings and thoughts of the research participants. At this point, while the data was being collected, the primary responsibility of the researcher was to protect the participants and their data. The mechanisms for such protection were clearly explained to the participants during the research process, and it was ensured that they were approved by the relevant research ethics review board before the research began (Sutton & Austin, 2015). Second, interview questions were asked to Turkish teachers in a consistent order and tone of voice. The researcher did not interfere with the views and answers of Turkish teachers, and he also avoided expressing his own feelings and thoughts. Finally, while analyzing the data, the researcher tried to present the data more objectively by seeking expert opinion during the interpretation and analysis of the data in order not to bring their own prejudices or certain dominant views of the participants to the fore.

3. Results

3.1 Findings Related to the Sample of the Study

40 teachers working in Idr province participated in the semi-structured interview form prepared for the compatibility of the 2019 Turkish Curriculum. Among the 40 Turkish teachers who participated in the interview, 25 are female and 15 are male. In terms of seniority, it is 1–9 years at most with 37 teachers, followed by 10–19 years with 2 teachers, and 20–29 years with 1 teacher. The education level of 38 of the 40 Turkish teachers who participated in the interview is undergraduate, and the education level of 2 teachers is graduate. The number of teachers who know the dialect and language characteristics of the region is 21, and the number of teachers who do not know is 19.

Table 1: Information on the Teachers Participating in the Research

Variables		F	%
Gender	Female	25	62,5
	Male	15	37,5
Seniority	1-9 years	37	92,5
	10-19	2	5
	20-29	1	2,5
Education	Undergraduate	38	95
	Graduate	2	5
Regional dialect features	Yes	21	52,5
	No	19	47,5

Out of 113 teacher opinions regarding the accessibility levels of achievements, 70 of them have a seniority of 1–9 years, 22 of them have a seniority of 10–19 years, 8 of them have a seniority of 20–29 years, 2 of them have a seniority of 30-39 years, and 1 of them has a seniority of 40 and above. The education level of 100 of the 113 Turkish teachers is an undergraduate degree, and the education level of 13 teachers is a graduate degree. The number of teachers who know the dialect and language characteristics of the region is 36; the number of teachers who partially know is 17, and the number of teachers who do not know is 60. This situation shows that the majority of the teachers whose opinions were taken do not know the dialect and language characteristics of the region.

3.2. Analysis of Findings Related to the Question "What is Curriculum Compatibility?", which is the main purpose of the research

When the answers to the question "What is the curriculum compatibility?" were examined, it was seen that the majority of Turkish teachers had no idea about the curriculum compatibility. (1-9, Undergraduate), 3(1-9, Undergraduate), 5(1-9, Undergraduate), 6 (1-9, Undergraduate) and 7 (1-9, Undergraduate) Turkish Teachers says "I don't know." When other keywords are examined, it is seen that the concepts related to program compatibility are not sufficient.

Figure 1: A sample of Turkish Word clouds of the answers to the question "What is the curriculum compatibility?"

When the N-gram counting analysis is examined, it is emphasized that the "courses" in the "curriculum" are "handled" "in parallel," and "importantly," the "chosen" "technique." If we express this as a Turkish teacher's (10

1–9 years old, postgraduate) sentences: "The curriculum and courses are taught in parallel, and the method in the curriculum is technical, and most importantly, to give lectures in accordance with the chosen approach."

Figure 2: A sample of Turkish N-gram counting analysis of answers to the question "What is curriculum compatibility?"

Undergraduate Turkish teacher 16 (1–9 years) says “the compatibility of the objectives and achievements of the program with the interests, wishes, and needs of the students.” Turkish teacher 26 (1–9 years, Undergraduate) states, “The curriculum may overlap with the practice.” Turkish teacher 31 (1–9 years, undergraduate) indicated, “It is compatible in terms of being able to use listening, reading, speaking, and writing skills throughout life.” Turkish teacher 37 (1-9 years old, undergraduate, female) emphasized that "the current curriculum is equivalent to the applied program, which means that it is compatible." Turkish teacher 38 (1-9 years, Undergraduate) states, “The acquisitions are appropriate for each grade level.” Turkish teacher 39 (1-9 years, Undergraduate) indicates, “The curriculum is compatible with the teaching.” Turkish teacher 40 (1-9 years, Bachelor) indicates that "the same for students throughout the country." From this point of view, it can be said that it is emphasized that the curriculum compatibility is compatible with the current program and the applied program and is suitable for the grade level.

Figure 3: A sample of Turkish topic model of answers to the question "What is curriculum compatibility?"

When the views of Turkish teachers were examined with theme (topic) model analysis, the concept of curriculum compatibility was emphasized as "the overlapping of the current curriculum with the curriculum-in-use, being appropriate for the grade level." For instance, rather than answering the question, Turkish Teacher 1 (29, 1-9 years, undergraduate) states, "The exam system and the curriculum are not compatible." Turkish teacher 4 (30, 1-9 years old, Bachelor) states, "A more equal distribution of the topics has been made in the fields of Turkish teaching compared to previous curricula." In this sense, the course and the content are transforming. Another Turkish teacher (12, 1-9 years old, Bachelor) states, "Turkish courses are progressing at a very slow pace." The subject of the 5th and 6th grades is very burdensome. "It is appropriate to give the grammar partially in the texts." These comments show that there is a lot of emphasis on the content. It suggests that their conceptual knowledge is not sufficient.

3.3. The Analysis of the Answers to the Question of "Do You Put Curriculum Compatibility in Practice? How?"

When the responses to the question "Do You Use Curriculum Compatibility?" were analyzed, When the question "How?" is posed, it is discovered that the majority of Turkish teachers believe they do this. Turkish teacher 10 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) stated this situation by saying, "Yes. "I try to practice each skill by allocating a certain amount of time." Turkish teacher 11 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) stated this situation by stating, "Yes. The curriculum's attainments at each grade level serve as the foundation for the next grade level's attainments. As a result, I try to provide the grade level's target achievements." He also stated that he realized it through the lens of gains.

When the question "Have you already examined the "Turkish Lesson Curriculum" of Turkish teachers? (Can you evaluate them in terms of achievements, visuals, and content?)" is examined, the fact that 33 of them stated that they examined it as an achievement and that they did not evaluate this confirms this situation. Again, when the 5-N-gram counting analysis is examined, it is seen that "to develop the student's comprehension and expression skills" is at the forefront. As emphasized by Turkish teacher 15 (1-9 years, undergraduate), "I try to make the lesson a little simpler by adapting the learning outcomes according to student levels." and Turkish teacher (30, aged 1-9 years, undergraduate) stated, "By managing an interactive process with the activities, I try to keep more students in the center and implement the curriculum." In this context, based on these comments, it can be assumed that students' levels and communication skills are important. When the topic model analysis is examined, it is seen that they achieve program compatibility by "solving the activities and getting support from the necessary resources," "allocating certain times," and "because it forms the basis for the achievements," "providing compatibility," and "coordination."

Turkish teacher 12 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) says, "I'm doing it." by reading the text appropriate to the curriculum and solving its activities. By getting support from additional resources when necessary and using activities and additional resources, Turkish teacher 15 (10-19 years old, undergraduate) stated, "I try to adapt the achievements according to the student's levels and make the lesson a little simpler." He claimed to have realized it within the context of gains. The Turkish teacher, 32 (1-9 years old, undergraduate), said, "No, it is not possible to do it completely." "Because it is necessary to plan these four basic skills as separate lessons." Turkish teacher 33 (1-9 years, undergraduate) similarly said, "Partly. "The gains are not very much." It is seen that he emphasizes the difficulty of raising money in terms of time. Turkish teacher 7 (1-9 years, undergraduate) said, "I can't answer because I don't know." Considering that three Turkish teachers gave similar answers, it can be said that they have problems achieving compatibility due to a lack of sufficient knowledge about the subject. According to this, Turkish teachers who said that they realized the compatibility of the curriculum expressed what they did within the framework of achievements, texts, and activities. Turkish teachers, who said that they could not achieve curriculum compatibility, had good knowledge of lesson planning, time, and sufficient knowledge.

3.4. The Analysis of the Answers to the Question "What are the Problems You Encounter Most While Implementing the Curriculum?"

When the analysis of the answers to the question "What are the most common problems you encounter while implementing the program?" was examined, it was noted that in the cloud analysis, reading and writing knowledge were most associated with inadequacy levels. When the answers to this question were analyzed, Turkish teacher

31 (1-9 years, undergraduate) stated that "There are problems in children's reading and writing due to the fact that substitute teachers from some village primary schools attend their lessons." A Turkish teacher of 30 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) stated that there is no student readiness by saying, "The conditions of the school and the level of the students make the teaching of some subjects difficult." "Many features of the region make the subject of proverbs and idioms difficult." Turkish teacher 35 (1-9 years, undergraduate) stated that "grammar subjects are emphasized too much in the coursebooks, and it makes teaching difficult." Similarly, Turkish teacher 36 (1-9 years, undergraduate) said, "Grammar subjects are difficult to understand." It is difficult to explain the subject of 7th grade verbs in the region. They do not understand the inflection of modals and subjects. I'm having a hard time figuring out the meaning of the question. "They cannot find the meaning of proverbs and idioms either." It is seen that the students mostly have problems expressing the grammar subjects. Based on the answers given, it is seen that Turkish teachers in the Idr region generally have problems with verbs, proverbs, and idioms. Another Turkish teacher, 38 (1-9 years old, undergraduate), said, "Grammar gains at grade levels are very high and difficult." Class hours are insufficient for students to acquire reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills. Elective courses can be added for these skills. Listening to texts is insufficient to gain listening skills. The proverbs and idioms are difficult for the children of this region to make sense of. "They speak their own language in class." He mentioned both grammar, proverbs, and idioms, as well as the lack of class hours for skill lessons. In addition, Turkish teacher 29 (1-9 years, undergraduate) says, "The curriculum and the examination system are not compatible, and the readiness levels of the students are not the same." It is understood that students have problems with reading, writing, and reading comprehension due to both the current exam system and the content of the program. This is because the 2019 Turkish curriculum, which wants the grammar acquisitions interspersed in the field of reading and writing skills in the program, contradicts the grammar activities included in the texts in the Turkish textbook. At the same time, the current exam system (LGS) is an exam for reading and reading comprehension skills. Furthermore, there is only one question about spelling and punctuation in the exam. Despite this, it is seen that grammar acquisitions are given a lot of space in both the Turkish curriculum and the Turkish course books.

When the N-gram counting results were examined, it was concluded that the students had difficulties in practice and that this might be related to local factors. In this regard, Turkish teacher 37 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) said, "Student levels are very low." The gains in the curriculum are very difficult and extensive. We cannot award achievements to illiterate students; instead, we must conduct literacy studies." achievement can we effectively give to an illiterate secondary school student?" and Turkish teacher 40 (1-9 years, undergraduate) said, "Student levels are different from each other. There are students who cannot read or write. There are also very good students. "The student's readiness is not sufficient, and he has no interest in the lesson." As he explained, it is evident that there is a problem in applying the student-based program. Likewise, teacher 15 (10-19 years old, undergraduate) emphasized that "students have not acquired the basic knowledge and skills that they should have in primary school, which has been a factor in the failure of the program to be implemented." Apart from this, Turkish teacher 13 (1-9 years, undergraduate) said, "When some reading texts do not attract the attention of village children, the lessons are not given fluently." "We are already having trouble reading because their mother tongue is Kurdish." Similarly, Turkish teacher 11 (1-9 years, undergraduate) said, "The fact that students have gains that do not attract their attention and that they will not use in their daily lives reduces the interest of students in some subjects." For example, grammar subjects (such as adjective, pronoun, adverb, and gerund)" and Turkish teacher 8 (1-9 years, undergraduate) said, "The lack of time in terms of economic conditions creates a problem in fully implementing the program." As emphasized in the following, it is seen that there are problems arising from both the curriculum and infrastructure reasons in the implementation of the program. When the thematic analysis is examined, it is seen that ideas such as lack of activity, lack of fluency in the lessons, the different mother tongues of the children, and the new Turkish curriculum are mostly emphasized in their comments. In this context, considering that their teachers are almost in a position to know the language characteristics of the region, it can be thought that the fact that Turkish teachers do not know the language characteristics of the region will cause a problem in the application of the program, and it can be said that the inadequacies in the previous educational applications may also be effective at this point.

3.5. Analysis of the Answers to the Question "Do You Have Any Recommendations for Preventing Curriculum Incompatibility?"

When the N-gram counting method and word cloud are examined, it is seen that reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills come to the fore. The reason for this is that, as stated by teacher 34 (1-9 years, undergraduate), "reading texts should be shorter at 6th and 7th grade levels." Grammar topics should be given less space. "Elective courses should be offered for reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills apart from the Turkish course" so that they can be related to the density of the grammar subjects. It has been seen that the needs of the region and the skills of reading, speaking, writing, and listening are highlighted. The Turkish teacher (30, aged 1-9) said, "The conditions of the schools and the level of student proficiency should be taken into account more, and a regional program should be prepared." He stated as follows: As Turkish teachers 21 and 22 pointed out by saying, "Conditions and needs of the region should be taken into account," and Turkish teacher 31 suggested, "Regional-specific programs can be prepared." Similarly, the needs of the region were emphasized in the N-gram counting cloud analysis. Reading, speaking, writing, and listening skills are emphasized. In this direction, Turkish teacher 8 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) said, "Doing research and investigations with a large team on enough samples in the field will lead to better results." As he stated, the importance of field work was emphasized. When the topic analysis was examined, it was seen that suggestions were given, such as taking regional needs into account, ensuring equality of opportunity, focusing on literacy skills, and changing the examination system while preparing the Turkish curriculum. When the answers to the question "Do you have any suggestions for preventing program incompatibility?" are examined, the Turkish language teacher 11 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) draws attention to the necessity of focusing on reading and comprehension studies through literary works instead of grammar by stating, "The influence of grammar issues should be reduced and more emphasis should be placed on reading and comprehension studies." "I think that teaching Turkish through literary works will contribute more to the language development of the student." Turkish teacher 12 (1-9 years, undergraduate) supported this idea by stating, "Some texts can be more meaningful and fun." Turkish teacher 34 (1-9 years, undergraduate) similarly stated, "Reading texts at 6th and 7th grade levels should be shorter." Grammar topics should be given less space. "Elective courses should be offered for reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills apart from the Turkish course." The proposal, Turkish Teacher 33 (1-9 years, undergraduate), states that "Examples of activities and sample lesson plans and methods and techniques for reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills can be included in the program." It emphasizes that the Turkish teaching program should be a guide for the teacher in terms of practice. In the third part of the 2006 Turkish Curriculum, there are headings for "Ataturkism," "Table of interdisciplinary field achievements matching the achievements of the Turkish Lesson Curriculum," "the role of the teacher in the implementation of the program," "the features that should be found in the reading texts," "the features that should be included in the content of the materials to be listened to or watched," "the contents that should be included in the 6th, 7th, and 8th grades," "themes," "methods and techniques," "activity examples," "the reading development file," "assessment and evaluation," "assessment and evaluation," "explanations about teaching a lesson," "lecture instruction sample," "dictionary," "methods Among these titles, "methods and techniques," "examples of activities," "reading development files," "assessment and evaluation," "explanations about teaching a lesson," and "an example of teaching a lesson" helped the teacher implement the program. Bulut (2019) drew attention to the fact that one of the outstanding features of the 2006 curriculum is the fact that it includes the type of text, methods, and techniques to be applied in the Turkish lesson. The purpose and application forms are also included in detail. According to Bac, Ayranc, and Mutlu (2017), "The methods and techniques of listening, watching, speaking, reading, and writing are included separately under the methods and techniques of the 2006 Turkish Curriculum, and examples of activities are presented separately for each learning area." is distinctive in a good way. In addition, the researchers stated that the 2006 curriculum's exemplary coursework process and various evaluation forms according to learning areas were the superior aspects of the TCC.

When analyzing the answers to the question, "Do you have any suggestions for preventing program incompatibility?" Turkish teacher 11 (1-9 years old, undergraduate) drew attention to the necessity of focusing on reading and comprehension studies through literary works instead of grammar by stating, "It is necessary to reduce the impact of grammar topics and give more weight to reading and comprehension studies." "I think that teaching Turkish through literary works will contribute more to the language development of the student." This idea is supported by the expressions of Turkish teacher 12 (1-9 years, undergraduate) stating that "some texts can be more meaningful and fun." and Turkish teacher 34 (1-9 years, undergraduate) stating that "reading texts should be shorter at 6th and 7th grade levels." Grammar topics should be given less space. "Elective courses should be offered for reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills apart from the Turkish course." Turkish Teacher 33 (1-9 years, undergraduate) states that "examples of activities and sample lesson plans and methods and techniques

for reading, listening, speaking, and writing skills can be included in the program." So he emphasizes that the Turkish teaching program should be a guide for the teacher in terms of practice. Under the third part of the 2006 Turkish Curriculum, there are the titles "Ataturkism," "Intermediate discipline field achievements table matching with the achievements of the Turkish Course Curriculum," "the role of the teacher in the implementation of the curriculum," "the features that should be found in the reading texts," "the features that should be in the content of the materials to be listened to or watched," "the contents that should be included in 6, 7, and 8th grades," "themes," "methods and techniques," "activity examples", "reading development file," "assessment and evaluation," "explanations about teaching a lesson," "lecture teaching example," " Among these titles, "methods and techniques", "examples of activity", "reading development file", "assessment and evaluation", "explanations about teaching a lesson" and "example of teaching a lesson" helped the teacher to implement the program. Bulut (2019) drew attention to the fact that one of the outstanding features of the 2006 curriculum is that it includes the text type, methods, and techniques to be applied in the Turkish lesson, as well as the purpose and application forms that are outlined in detail. According to Bac, Ayranc, and Mutlu (2017), "The methods and techniques of listening, watching, speaking, reading, and writing are included separately under the methods and techniques of the 2006 Turkish Curriculum, and examples of activities are presented separately for each learning area." is distinctive in a good way. In addition, the researchers stated that the 2006 curriculum's exemplary coursework process and various evaluation forms according to learning areas are the superior aspects of the curriculum.

3.6. Findings of Teachers' Opinions on Outcomes of the Curriculum

The frequently repeated acquisitions for speaking skills (5.6.7 and 8th grades) are given in Table 2.

Table 2: The frequently repeated acquisitions for speaking skills (5.6.7 and 8th grades)

		Yes		Partially		No	
		f	%	f	%	F	%
1	Suggests different titles for what they listen/watch.	45	40,2	39	34,8	28	25
2	Makes predictions about the development of events when they listen/watch.	28	25	53	47,3	31	27,7
3	Determines the subject of what they listen/watch.	36	32,1	47	42	29	25,9
4	Summarizes what they have listened/watched.	35	31,3	49	43,8	28	25
5	Answers questions about what they have listened/watched.	43	38,4	40	35,7	29	25,9
6	Vivifies the narrative texts that he/she listens/watches.	34	30,4	37	33	41	36,6
7	Comprehends the speaker's non-verbal messages.	38	33,9	37	33	37	33
8	He/she reports his/her opinions about what they listen/watch.	40	35,7	46	41,1	26	23,2
9	Evaluates the content of what they listen/watch.	34	30,4	45	40,2	33	29,5
10	Implements listening strategies.	36	32,1	41	36,6	35	31,3
11	He/she determines the main idea/main sense of what he/she listens/watches.	40	35,7	38	33,9	34	30,4

In order to analyze the data in the table more clearly, the percentage contributions of all items were added together, divided by the product of 100 by the number of items, and multiplied by 100 (total percentage/(number of items*100))*100. Thus, the frequency ratio of each dimension was expressed as a percentage. Accordingly, when the total score percentages related to the listening and watching skills were taken as the basis of the question, it was seen that the percentage was partially emphasized in the expression. When the table above is examined, 40.2% of the first learning outcome is yes, the second outcome is "partially yes" with a percentage of 47.3%, the third outcome is "partially yes" with a percentage of 42%, the fourth outcome is "partially yes" with a percentage of 43.8%, the fifth outcome is "yes" with a percentage of 38.4%, the sixth outcome is "no" with a percentage of 36.6%, the seventh outcome is "yes" Figure 4 indicates that when the percentage expression of the sum of the percentages of the scores for the listening/watching skill was examined by taking the question as the basis, it was seen that the expression "partially yes" was dominant..

Figure 4: Expressing the sum of the percentages of the scores for the Listening/Watch skill as a percentage based on the question

The frequently repeated acquisitions for speaking skills (5.6.7 and 8th grades) are given in Table 3.

Table 3: The frequently repeated acquisitions for speaking skills (5.6.7 and 8th grades)

Acquisitions for Speaking Skills	Yes		Partially Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%	F	%
12 In his speeches, he uses Turkish words instead of words taken from foreign languages that have not yet settled in our language.	36	32,1	42	37,5	34	30,4
13 Uses words according to their meanings.	41	36,6	38	33,9	33	29,5
14 S/hee gives a prepared speech.	38	33,9	45	40,2	29	25,9
15 S/he gives spontanous speech.	29	25,9	52	46,4	31	27,7
16 He uses body language effectively in his speeches.	37	33	39	34,8	36	32,1
17 Uses appropriate transitional and linking expressions in his speech.	41	36,6	39	34,8	32	28,6
18 Implements speaking strategies.	37	33	34	30,4	41	36,6

In order to analyze the data in the table more clearly, the percentage contributions of all items were added together, divided by the product of 100 by the number of items, and multiplied by 100 (total percentage/(number of items*100))*100. Thus, the frequency ratio of each dimension was expressed as a percentage. Accordingly, when the sum of the percentages for speaking skills is taken as the basis of the question, it is seen that the percentage is partially emphasized in the expression. When the table above is examined, the 13th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 36,6%, the 14th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 40,2%, the 15th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 46,4%, the 16th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 34,8%, the 17th outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 36,6%, and the 18th outcome is "no" with the percentage of 36,6%. When the percentage expression of the sum of the percentages of the scores in speaking skill was taken as the basis of the question, it was seen that the expression was partially dominant.

Figure 5: Expressing the sum of the percentages of the scores on the speaking skill as a percentage based on the questions

The frequently repeated acquisitions for reading skills (5.6.7 and 8th grades) were given in Table 4.

Table 4: The frequently repeated acquisitions for reading skills (5.6.7 and 8th grades)

Learning Outcomes for Reading Skills	Yes		Partially Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%	F	%
19 Reads aloud and silently, paying attention to punctuation marks.	38	33,9	38	33,9	36	32,1
20 Reads the text in accordance with the characteristics of the genre.	38	33,9	37	33	37	33
21 Applies reading strategies.	37	33	37	33	38	33,9
22 Reads texts written in different fonts.	39	34,8	38	33,9	35	31,3
23 Determines the contribution of idioms and proverbs to the meaning of the text.	36	32,1	41	36,6	35	31,3
24 Guess the meaning of unfamiliar words and phrases using the context.	43	38,4	31	27,7	38	33,9
25 Predicts the subject of the text to be read from the visual and the title.	46	41,1	34	30,4	32	28,6
26 Asks questions about the text.	43	38,4	39	34,9	30	26,8
27 Answers questions about the text.	52	46,4	33	29,5	27	24,1
28 Determines the subject of the text.	36	32,1	52	46,4	24	21,4
29 Determines the main idea / main emotion of the text.	35	31,3	44	39,3	33	29,5
30 Determines the appropriate title for the content of the text.	49	43,8	36	32,1	27	24,1
31 Identifies the story elements in the text.	41	36,6	45	40,2	26	23,2
32 Answers questions about the image.	48	42,9	36	32,1	28	25
33 Comprehends the way of emphasizing important points in the text.	40	35,7	30	26,8	42	37,5
34 Makes comparisons between texts.	40	35,7	37	33	35	31,3
35 Uses information resources effectively.	32	28,6	37	33	43	38,4
36 Distinguish the real and fictional elements in the text.	45	40,2	36	32,1	31	27,7
37 Distinguish between text types.	39	34,8	41	36,6	32	28,6

When the table above is examined, 19th outcome is “partially yes” with the percentage of 33,9%, 20th outcome is “partially yes” with the percentage of 33,9%, 21th outcome is “no” with the percentage of 33,9%, 22th outcome is “yes” with the percentage of 34,8%, 23th outcome is “partially yes” with the percentage of 36,6%, 24th outcome is “yes” with the percentage of 38,4%, 25th outcome is “yes” with the percentage of 41,1%, 26th outcome is “yes”

with the percentage of 38,4%, 27th outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 46,4%, 28th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 46,4%, 29th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 39,3%, 30th outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 43,4%, 31th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 40,2%, 32th outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 42,9%, 33th outcome is "no" with the percentage of 37,5%, 34th outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 35,7%, 35th outcome is "no" with the percentage of 38,4%, 36th outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 40,2%, 37th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 36,6%. When the percentage expression of the sum of the percentages of the scores for the reading skill was taken as the basis of the question, it was seen that the expression "Yes" was dominant.

Figure 6: Expressing the sum of the percentages of the scores for the reading skill as a percentage

The most frequent Learning Outcomes for Writing Skill (5.6.7 and 8th) are given Table 5.

Table 5: The most frequent Learning Outcomes for Writing Skill (5.6.7 and 8th)

Learning Outcomes for Writing Skills	Yes		Partially Yes		No	
	f	%	f	F	%	F
38 He writes poetry.	39	34,8	42	37,5	31	27,7
39 Writes short texts.	37	33	41	36,6	34	30,4
40 Writes narrative text.	47	42	35	31,3	30	26,8
41 Implements writing strategies.	41	36,6	30	26,8	41	36,6
42 Fills the forms in accordance with the instructions.	50	44,6	34	30,4	28	25
43 Determines a suitable title for the content of what you write.	53	47,3	32	28,6	27	24,1
44 He shares what he wrote.	52	46,4	33	29,5	27	24,1
45 Edits what he wrote.	33	29,5	37	33	42	37,5
46 Writes informative texts.	31	27,7	38	33,9	43	38,4

When the table above is examined, the 38th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 37.5%, the 39th outcome is "partially yes" with the percentage of 36.6%, the 40th outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 42%, the 41st outcome is "yes" and "no" with the same percentage of 36.6%, the 42nd outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 44.6%, the 43rd outcome is "yes" with the percentage of 47%. When the percentage expression of the sum of the percentages of the scores for the writing skill was examined by taking the question as the basis, it was seen that the expression "Yes" was dominant.

Figure 7: Expressing the sum of the percentages of the scores for the writing skill as a percentage

4. Discussion And Conclusion

From the word cloud analysis of the answers to the question "What is curriculum compatibility?" it was seen that teachers have no idea about program compatibility. Since it focuses on a single word, it can be justified that no meaningful concept emerges, or it can be concluded that the participants do not really have enough information on this subject. In this respect, when we look at the n-gram counting method, we see that the curriculum and the lessons are processed in parallel, and the method in the program is technical and, most importantly, it gives lessons in accordance with the chosen approach. Similarly, when the topic model and possible scenarios are considered, it is emphasized that the curriculum overlaps and is suitable for the grade level. When the participant comments are examined, it is seen that their statements emphasize the content element of the program in terms of intensity and time. As a result, curriculum compatibility with the n-gram counting method is considered to be both temporal and methodological. Temporal compatibility is an important concept here because it shows that teachers see themselves as passive practitioners in the curriculum. Likewise, although some of the teachers refer to the student orientation of the program as "the compatibility of the objectives and achievements of the program with the interests, wishes, and needs of the students," they show that they neglect the teacher aspect of the program, namely teacher agency, because the curriculum is viewed as a passive document that can be read and directly implemented. Curriculum compatibility, as Lezotte (2002) emphasizes, can be compared to the process of starting with the finished product (the student being assessed) and tracing back steps to clearly visualize the learning journey in ways that are meaningful to the teacher. The teacher should commit to asking himself what evidence will be needed to test the range of students' knowledge acquisition and synthesis. This process will enable the teacher to confidently determine what kind of degree of matching exists between the intended curriculum and the evaluated curriculum. As Lezotte (2002:9) reiterates, as a teacher, one must be convinced in his or her mind and heart that if s/he teaches the targeted curriculum and the students learn about it, they will perform well on the assessment criteria. When it is considered that a teacher or a group of teachers are active, making choices or taking a stance in this context in a way that may affect their work and professional identity (Eteläpelto, Vähäsantanen, Hokkä, & Paloniemi, 2013; cited in Bellibaş, Gümüş, & Caliskan, 2019), a teacher-centered approach is emphasized at this point. It can be said that one reason for this is the teacher's expectation to be an intermediary that implements the central curriculum. At this point, it has been observed that teachers mostly refer to Posner's (2004) Official Curriculum (Clear—Written) and Curriculum in Practice (Real Program), and they emphasize the Neglected Curriculum (Null) in terms of content and time. For this reason, it can be concluded that there is a problem between the official and the neglected curriculum, that the reason is due to the content of the curriculum, and that they perceive the compatibility of the curriculum as the overlap between the applied program and the official program. "The concept of curriculum compatibility is explained as the curriculum determined centrally by the ministries of education and the curriculum applied by the teachers in the teaching process" (zpolat Turan & Bay, 2015). In this regard, it can be said that teachers have an understanding of curriculum compatibility according to this definition. It should be noted that teachers express curriculum commitment more than compatibility. However, it can be said

that the concept of curriculum compatibility is considered here as a central program implementation algorithm. There are different levels of curriculum compatibility, however. According to Fraser and Bosanquet (2006), the first level of it expresses the content and structure of a single unit. The second category focuses on curriculum-level content and structure. Both categories require a product-based understanding of the program. In the third category, the curriculum is understood in terms of the student's learning experience. The fourth category, curriculum, approaches the co-construction of knowledge between student and teacher. These last two categories are characterized by a process-based approach. According to Biggs and Tang (2007), curriculum compatibility—the constructive consistency between teaching, learning, and assessment—is a crucial aspect of the quality of teaching. In order for the learning objectives to become real learning outcomes and thus optimize students' learning, it is important to make sure that each activity helps to achieve the learning objectives (Wijngaards-de Meij & Merx, 2018). At this point, it can be concluded that teachers' perceptions of curriculum coherence are at the level of the first two structures; very few of them point to the third level by emphasizing the student; and they neglect the fourth category by not making enough reference to teacher activity. For this reason, it can be stated that teachers look at product-based program compatibility and neglect process-based harmony.

Figure 8: Findings suggest that teachers have a product-based understanding of curriculum compatibility.

However, the harmony between the intended and evaluated training programs should not be read as a one-way process. This is not only the case of teachers showing that they are fully aware of the expectations of the curriculum developers, but also the case that other stakeholders themselves are fully aware of the content of the curriculum and the teaching method. The curriculum ensures that appropriate levels are set between instruction and assessment. Therefore, the prerequisite for any coherent educational strategy is that the goal of providing every student with learning opportunities and justifying their achievements can be fulfilled.

When we look at the analysis of the answers to the question, "Do You Put Curriculum Compatibility into Practice? How?" The word cloud analysis shows that the majority of Turkish teachers think that they do this. When the 5-N-gram counting analysis is examined, it is seen that "to develop students' comprehension and expression skills" is at the forefront. Again, when the topic analysis is examined, it is seen that they achieve program compatibility by "solving the activities and getting support from the necessary resources," "allocating certain times," and "because it forms the basis for the achievements," "providing compatibility," and "coordination." From this point of view, it can be stated that teachers emphasize instructional adaptability. In instructional compatibility, it can be said that the compatibility between teaching and assessments is mostly mentioned, while the expression of program compatibility has a more general framework, and it can be said that the harmony here covers all the elements (zpolat Turan and Bay, 2015: 19). At this point, there are two types of fit: internal and external. Internal compatibility is the process of ensuring that teaching and learning activities, assessments, and goals are compatible, while external compatibility is derived from a single course (e.g., basic concepts of physiology,

professional skills) that points to standardized factors that are independent (Shaltry, 2020). For this reason, it can be said that teachers mostly emphasize inner harmony when it comes to the compatibility of goals. In addition, stating that the acquisitions are realized within the framework of texts and activities shows that teachers only adhere to the texts and activities in the textbook. The absence of alternative activities and studies may be an indication of a one-dimensional approach.

When the analysis of the answers to the question “What are the most common problems you encounter while implementing the program?” was examined, it was noted that in the cloud analysis, reading and writing knowledge were most associated with the inadequacy levels of the students. When the N-gram counting results were examined, it was concluded that the students had difficulties in practice and that this might be related to local factors. When teacher statements were examined, it was seen that this was mainly associated with achievements being higher than student competencies. In addition, it contradicts the 2019 Turkish Curriculum, which wants the grammar acquisitions interspersed in reading and writing skills and the grammar activities included in the context of the text in the Turkish textbook. However, the current exam system (LGS) is an exam for reading and reading comprehension skills. It is seen that there is only one problem with spelling and punctuation. Despite this, giving too much space to grammar acquisitions in both the Turkish Curriculum and the Turkish course book leads to the conclusion that it is inconsistent. Similarly, when the topic analysis is examined, there are ideas such as lack of activity, not being fluent in the lessons, the mother tongue of the some of the children being Kurdish, and the newness of the Turkish curriculum. It was stated that there were more problems with grammar, proverbs, and idioms. It can be thought that the fact that Turkish teachers do not know the language characteristics of the region will cause a problem in the application of the curriculum, and it can be said that the inadequacies in the previous educational curricula may also be effective. At this point, it can be said that the flexibility of the training program is emphasized. The flexibility of the education program means that it can be arranged according to the economic and social characteristics of the region as well as the interests and needs of the students. In addition, a training program should assist practitioners and be applicable. In this respect, it can be said that teachers have problems in terms of flexibility, helpfulness, and applicability of the Turkish education program. In the study of Avc (2018), in which he examined the views of teachers and students on teaching the 5th grade Turkish lesson in the context of the Turkish curriculum (2018), the curriculum did not meet socio-cultural differences, was not compatible with individual needs, and teachers did not conduct the course in accordance with the program's approach or the course content from time to time stated that it was above the student level and reached similar findings. In the study of Menteşe (2013), in which the opinions of the teachers about the Turkish lesson curriculum were examined, it was determined that students encounter different problems, such as unequal levels and not finding the course materials sufficient.

When the analysis of the answers to the question “Do you have any suggestions for preventing program incompatibility?” is examined, it is seen that reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills come to the fore in the N-gram counting method and word cloud method. When the topic analysis was examined, it was seen that suggestions were given, such as taking into account regional needs, ensuring equality of opportunity, focusing on literacy skills, and changing the exam system while preparing the Turkish curriculum. In this regard, it can be said that teachers focus on skills rather than knowledge and emphasize that regional differences and needs should be taken into account. When the percentage expression of the sum of the percentages of the scores for listening and speaking skills is examined by taking the question as the basis, it is seen that the expression is partially dominant. When the percentage expression of the sum of the percentages of the scores for reading and writing skills is examined by taking the question as the basis, it is seen that the expression "yes" is dominant. In this respect, it can be stated that while the teachers see the program as more positive in terms of reading and writing skills, it is partially positive in terms of listening, watching, and speaking skills. However, it should be emphasized that the rates are close to each other. In the study of Dur (2014), in which primary and secondary school teachers, students, and parents' views on the renewed Turkish curriculum and its implementation were examined, it was determined that teachers reported positive opinions about reading, speaking, and writing achievements but partially positive opinions about listening and watching achievements, which is in line with the findings of this study. Er (2011) stated in his study that it is difficult to use measurement tools in the field of listening and watching learning, and that it is therefore necessary to increase the number of listening and watching texts, decrease the number of activities, include interesting text types, and increase the required time. They revealed that textbooks should be prepared according to the characteristics of the regions. Different in-service activities and incentives should be

developed to increase teachers' experiential and theoretical knowledge and motivation regarding curriculum compatibility. While updating the curriculum, the opinions and suggestions of Turkish teachers about the program should be taken into account. In order to improve listening/watching, speaking, reading, and writing skills in the curriculum, improvements should be made by considering student needs, regional differences, and current problems. Curriculum compatibility focuses on curriculum and instruction. Therefore, teachers should know how to teach better as well as what students need to learn. Planning the curriculum contents according to the best method, technique, and strategy in teaching also makes it necessary to use time effectively. Teachers need time to spread this knowledge throughout the school year to increase student success. Curriculum compatibility should be left to teachers. Thus, teachers should be empowered to carry out the adaptation process and ensure consistency throughout the entire academic year.

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